
Research

Impact of Public parks in fighting Climate change in Rwanda

Guillaume Niyontezeho^{1*}, Sissoko Bourema¹, James Ngabo²

¹Southwest Forestry University

²University of Lay Adventists of Kigali

Abstract: Public parks are important to urban environments, residents, and visitors. Among other functions, they provide environmental services, in the era where the earth is facing challenges of climate change that are caused by global warming public parks can play a significant role in reducing the climate change effects. This paper identifies the development of public parks in the east African region, particularly in the country of Rwanda Kigali city. The paper argues that the continual growth of Kigali city should not be a hindrance to the development of parks. A number of factors are important to consider when building efficient parks, these include park accessibility, park usability and park sustainability. The paper concludes by offering policy suggestions as to how to resolve the dearth of parks and green spaces in the city region.

Keywords: Climate change, Public parks, Rwanda, global warming

Corresponding Author:

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Introduction

In 2021, the state of the climate in Africa indicated that 28 African countries provide basic to critical climate services, with only 9 providing comprehensive services. Only four countries have advanced capabilities to provide end-to-end drought forecasting or warning systems [1]. While Fig. 1 illustrates that climate change and CO₂ consequences are pervasive across urban and regional Africa, and the World Economic Forum described Africa as being in the eye of the climate change storm in 2018, the continent's fast-increasing conurbations remain the most vulnerable in the world[2]. In 2020, the African urbanization rate was expected to be at 47% on average. Since 2000, the number of people living in cities has been gradually increasing, and this trend is expected to continue in the coming years. Burundi, Niger, Uganda, Tanzania, and Burkina Faso are seeing particularly rapid urbanization. In these nations, the urban population increased by more than 4% in 2020 compared to the previous year. Lagos, Nigeria, is Africa's largest city, with a population of over nine million people. Kinshasa, in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Cairo, in Egypt, both have over seven million people[3]. Furthermore, other cities on the continent are fast expanding. Between 2020 and 2035, the population of Bujumbura, Burundi, is expected to expand by 123%, the fastest rate on the continent., In the 1990s, the unfathomable effects of climate change were on the necks of African cities (Cobbinah 2021), and today, 79 out of 86 African cities are among the world's fastest developing conurbations that are threatened by extreme risk due to climate change.[4,5]

Fig. 1: CO2 emissions in Africa

Conceptual framework: Public parks in fighting climate changes in cities

Considering rising sea levels, rising temperatures, variable precipitation regimes generating catastrophic flooding and extended droughts, and threatening rapidly growing populations and economic prospects, strengthening resilience is the continent’s major survival strategy. Despite being signatories to all transnational climate accords for instance the 2016 Paris Climate Agreement and the 1995 Kyoto Protocol [6]national governments’ efforts to adopting urban resilience plans have been uninspiring (Addaney and Cobbinah 2019). There has been a lot of writing focused on resolving climate change challenges, particularly those connected to drought and flood. This can be explained by the fact that African countries account for half of the world’s low-income countries, which means that the population that still struggles to feed their families and deal with drought would include more farmers rather than city dwellers who are concerned with how much they earn per month. According to the UN report 2022, 21% of the African continent’s population is food insecure, while 60% live in rural regions and farming is the primary economic activity. This leads to the reason why farmers are more vulnerable to climate change. However, the economy of African countries before covid 19 was growing substantially and doubling the world’s GDP growth, as the GDP growth gets on the rise the rural-urban migration also follows. Africa has the world’s fastest urban growth rate, with an additional 950 million people living in African cities by 2050, and small and medium-sized communities are seeing the majority of this increase, according to the World Bank. Africa’s urbanization brings both benefits and challenges. People from rural areas move to cities as countries progress to middle-income status, making them more vulnerable, especially if steps for sustainable urban planning are not adopted. To facilitate this global response, particularly in Africa, UN Secretary-General António Guterres convened a climate meeting in 2019 attended by world leaders, corporate sector officials, and civil society representatives to strengthen and accelerate action on climate change. This summit stressed six main topics of discussion, the most important of which were cities and resilience[7] Africa’s potential to socioenvironmental transformations may come as a result of increased resilience building due to the fact of her stature as a continent with fastest growing cities. The goal of this research is to provide a unique perspective on the context of green urban planning and to convince policymakers to prioritize sustainability for urban development. Urban

planning, refers to a highly political activity that frequently comprises the formulation of conceptual standards for space and how these norms are applied in space through state control [8]. This study is of interest to scholars working on broad climate resilient development issues in Africa's metropolitan space. This article highlights the importance of urban planning in developing climate resilient action in African cities from this perspective.

Climate change has emerged as the world's most significant environmental concern, as well as one of our generation's most pressing social, economic, and health challenges. While it is a global issue, its local consequences are felt the most profoundly. The effects of climate change are very real and very personal, affecting everyone from families uprooted by flooding to elderly grandparents hospitalized due to health difficulties caused by high heat. While the effects of climate change are frightening, there is growing acknowledgment that parks can help to solve the problem. Parks minimize harmful carbon pollution that contributes to climate change; they protect people and infrastructure from increasingly severe storms, sea-level rise, heat waves, and droughts; and they directly address some of the key public health concerns that climate change exacerbates. According to a study by American planning association, public parks have proven to highly contribute in reducing climate change effects in cities. The study argues that "Parks are the first and best line of defense against these changes" as much as public parks contribute to decreasing climate change effects, public parks serve to bring about social cohesion and create stronger ties among people, according to people who live nearby parks tend to have lower anxiety and less physical disorder (WorldBank, 2017).

Parks in the cities of east Africa

The growth of public parks in East Africa can be traced back to the colonial era, when there were few. Their scarcity is determined by colonial, in which the rulers would develop urban planning and public parks to serve as a buffer between themselves and the natives. They would accomplish this by locating green spaces such as horse racing tracks, cricket ovals, and golf courses. Africa and India were more prone to this. African cities have suffered from more severe urban planning, which has hampered their right to a rich city life. Nonetheless, the city of Nairobi constructed the 5 acre Jee Gradeens public park, which was donated by Albhai Mullah Jeevanjee in 1906.[9] Other public parks were constructed in the years that followed, including the 30-acre Nairobi National Arboretum, which was established in 1907, and

Nairobi City Park, which was established in 1921. It is no wonder that Nairobi is renowned as the green city in the sun; not only does it have national parks, but it also has several other large-scale public gardens, such as the 12.9 ha Uhuru gardens (built in 1969), the Karura rainforest on the city limits, and paradise park. Among other urban parks and gardens, Nairobi city has a number of golf courses, including Windsor, Royal Nairobi, Karen County, Vet lab, Kenyan railway, Sigona, and Muthaiga. Kenya's scenario is similar to that of Uganda's capital city, Kampala. The city's natural environment has been destroyed as a result of the city's continued urbanization. Kampala's urbanization has contributed significantly to the deterioration of the city's natural environment[10]. The Kampala Metropolitan Area now has a population of three million people, with a growth rate of five million predicted over the next ten years. In early 2013, the Kampala City Capital Authority (KCCA) initiated a program to restore and revitalize the city's public green and open areas. The new Kampala physical plan plans out public green and open areas throughout the greater Kampala cosmopolitan area. The Sheraton Hotel Gardens was repossessed by KCCA in November 2013, with plans to renovate and reopen it to the public as an open park. three gazed public parks near the city center from private developers, are among others the KCCA intend to reclaim including Centenary Park, Wandegeya, and Kamwokya Children's Park. In public debates, no clear, shared view of the function of urban public parks has emerged. While the focus on small ancient perception is that they are made for children to play and adults to sit and relax adding to the beatification of the city it in unclear how wetlands would fit in this context. for Wetlands preserve biodiversity, reduce air pollution and can provide recreational and physical activities for children and adults in Kampala[7].

Nevertheless, according to city officials, there are 32 parks across the city and they are divided into the regions central (7), kawempe(3), Lubaga(7), and Makindye(6). However, according to the audit conducted there was a witness of 26 parks locations was only able to establish the locations of 26 parks.

Factors of that show a useful public park

- **Parks accessibility**

As stated by [11] Cities can be defined as the interconnections of social, ecological, and technological systems, Many cities have the feature of bringing buildings and highways to the forefront. Highways and overpasses are frequently built through inner-city residential districts to improve motorized traffic circulation, resulting in extensive demolition of low-income slum areas for redevelopment, despite the negative social and environmental effects of these new routes[12] The loss of the shared environment, reduced pedestrian access, energy depletion, traffic congestion, and an increase in the likelihood of accidents are among the repercussions[13]. While several cities have replaced deteriorating elevated roadways with tunnels or park-like boulevards, officials in numerous other towns are still building increasingly unconnected networks of urban expressways and overpasses[14]. For most urban residents, going to work or using public facilities is a daily activity[15]. The accessibility of recreational venues is extremely important in terms of their use rates and people' health[16]. As a result, discussions regarding how to make parks more accessible to city dwellers and how to inform planning strategies on the effects of various urban street-network systems on park accessibility continue. Previously conducted research examined physical accessibility in a variety of ways. Many studies have used simple calculation methods, such as the shortest origin to destination (OD) metric distance, such as Euclidean distance[17], street network distance, and cost-weighted distance. Furthermore, a number of researchers used more complex approaches that combined physical distance and other data, such as physical constraints to accessibility inside and outside parks[18], psychological possibilities, and institutional barriers to park access. Traversing the spatial arrangements of cities[19]. These indicators are highly related to people's preferences for pedestrian route selection and observed movement flows [20]

- **Parks usability**

People can visit public urban parks to achieve one or more of the following objectives: culture, recreation, social, heritage, and education. There should be a balance between park zones and different amenities to meet all the roles of park especially for citizens with the greatest needs such as low-income people, elderly and persons with disabilities.[21] There is reasons that lead people to visit public parks. among others are culture, recreation, social. With those reasons can come the challenges and to overcome them there will be the need of increasing the usability. Data was collected and observed from 174 parks design sand human behaviors in 25 cities across the country. The study found and recommended that park design; park program; marketing; and measuring park use are the four main aspects that can affect park usability[22] .

- **Parks sustainability**

Sustainable development in planning and development of urban parks According to Satterthwaite (1999), there are three major aspects that can lead to the sustainable development. These aspects include: meeting people needs and preferences; sustaining the natural environment in its local, regional and national levels; and sustaining the cultural values. The principle of sustainable development should be addressed in the planning and development of urban public parks to improving the quality of places where people live and work. Urban green parks contribute to ecological sustainability. Ensuring the continuous usability of the urban public park is important to maintain the ecological sustainability within the city. Development of sustainable urban spaces should be based on a balanced relationship between both human need sand the environmental value of biodiversity[23]. To achieve this balance, the

designing and developing of public parks need to follow the three dimensions of sustainable development (social, economic and environmental) at the same time. Sustainable urban parks should be self-sufficient, adapted to the local condition and subjected to a continuous low cost maintenance program[24]. Benefits from sustaining urban public parks Well-designed and maintained public parks according to users' needs and adapted with the natural environment will provide useable green spaces that have positive impacts on human beings and the natural environment. These positive effects include improving human physical and mental health, improving air quality and preserving the biodiversity. Improving the quality of urban park has also economic benefits through encouraging tourism, attracting and retaining businesses in the area, creating jobs opportunities, and increasing the surrounding land and property value. Moreover, urban parks may have educational benefits as they can be used to be an outdoor classroom for schools and universities for practicing environmental studies or making research projects. The aim of the educational experience is to connect young people with the natural world so that they could understand the value and importance of sustainable environment. Therefore, Urban Parks can be seen as open-air laboratories for biologists, geographers, environmentalists as well as social scientists [25]

Research context: Kigali city

Kigali was founded in 1907 as a German colonial outpost and trading center. Because of its strategic location, it grew over time into a significant commercial center. According to Bindseil (1988), Kigali was also a convenient transportation hub for commercial activities involving Bukoba, Kigoma (Tanzania), and Bujumbura (Burundi), as well as Kisangani (Democratic Republic of the Congo) and Kampala (Uganda). As a result, many Arab and Indian traders relocated to the city. Belgian troops defeated the Germans in the First World War in 1916, and Rwanda came under Belgian colonial control. Kigali became Rwanda's capital following the country's independence in 1962. [26]. During the colonial period, the city grew slowly and had only 6,000 inhabitants in 1962, concentrated within a 2.5 km² boundary at the top of Nyarugenge hill. The period following independence saw rapid population growth as well as spatial expansion. However, the post-1990s period saw a sharp increase in the rate of urbanization, particularly after the 1994 genocide, when thousands of refugees returned to the city, primarily for safety reasons. Kigali is currently the country's largest urban agglomeration. In 2012, the capital of Rwanda had a population of 1,132,686 people, but by 2017 it had grown to 1,631,657 people, spread across an area of 730 km² [27]. Kigali, as the country's capital and primary city, remains an appealing destination for visitors from all over the country due to its strategic location and concentration of a diverse range of economic activities. Since 1978, it has housed roughly half of the country's urban population. However, unprecedented urban growth has resulted in an increase in informal settlements and a haphazard urban land use pattern, which accounts for approximately 60% of the city's built-up space [28]. This uncontrolled growth has presented numerous challenges to the government's plan to ensure these cities' long-term viability.

According to data estimates, Rwanda's urbanization rate will rise from around 18.4 percent today to 35 percent by 2024. [7]. has one of the highest annual urban growth rates in East Africa, with an estimated 4.5 percent. Rwanda's Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (2013-2018) identified six secondary cities as potential urban growth poles to reduce migration to the capital city and develop opportunities in Rwanda's mostly border cities: Huye, Muhanga, Musanze, Nyagatare, Rubavu, and Rusizi [29]. The populations of these secondary cities contribute 13% of the country's GDP [7] and account for a quarter of the country's urban population.

Public spaces in Gasabo District

Source: Kigali city

Public open spaces in Kicukiro District

Source: Kigali city
Nyarugenge public open spaces

Source: Kigali city

Kigali: Towards City-Wide Public Space Strategy

The City of Kigali is constantly working on steps to construct new public open spaces for its citizens. The city worked along with its citizens in designating places that may serve as public open spaces during the master plan revision process. Results of the participatory method are fully incorporated in the new masterplan, where vital public places for the city are designated. The “City for Citizens” is among eight aims that have been established to drive the Kigali City Master plan, to enhance accessibility to equitable urban opportunities and services and to inspire public engagement in the planning process. These and other open spaces in the city were documented by the City of Kigali in collaboration with the Global Green Growth Institute as a first step toward a much larger action-oriented plan for the

city's public open spaces, including "urban pockets": small public open spaces serving primarily the local population. According to research from the Rwandan government, public spaces have a significant role in preserving social cohesion and wellness, with several benefits for safety, public health, the environment, and other areas. The City of Kigali is committed to ensuring that everyone has access to green spaces and public areas that are safe, welcoming, and accessible, especially for women, children, older people, and people with disabilities. To cut down on greenhouse gas emissions and encourage more use of public open space, the City of Kigali has established a "car-free zone" in the heart of the city. A bimonthly event sponsored by the City of Kigali encourages residents of metropolitan areas to spend time outside for activities like sporting events, exhibitions, and performances. The City of Kigali has unveiled an initiative, "KigaliYacu: Activating Public Outdoor Space One Bench at a Time". Re-imagining and re-engaging the street as a public open space is the goal of the effort. Through an infrastructure intervention, such as a seating area, the initiative is seeking suggestions for how to turn the street into a public space. Designing a public space that can influence and change the street's dynamics while igniting and sustaining social and cultural exchanges. When public open spaces are planned and put into place, those elements ought to be included. Public open spaces must be prioritized more urgently in national and green city development initiatives.

The data indicate that there are roughly 100 public and open places dispersed over the three districts of Gasabo, Kicukiro, and Nyarugenge in the city of Kigali[30]. Our research revealed that approximately 90% of Kigali's public parks have easy access to the city's main road or are connected to it by steps, making it convenient for people to visit. As a result of their utility, parks are regularly visited since there is a demand for them; yet, some of them are difficult to use at night because of a lack of lighting. The research also demonstrates the lack of infrastructure and facilities, such as street lighting, accessible restrooms, and safe access for individuals with disabilities (handrails, ramps, signage). In terms of sustainability, there is a lack of upkeep of the few public parks that are now available; when you visit one, the green area is no longer green but rather more of a public space. In order to exploit the wetlands in Kigali city, maintain the greenery there, and address the effects of climate change, the Rwandan government has put in place plans to establish five eco-public parks in the wetlands available in Kigali city.

Public parks use in Kigali city in relation climate change

Limited land surface and rural poverty cause rural-urban migration. Despite Rwanda's green city and building rules, rising urbanization is pushing additional greenhouse gas (GHG) emission sources such as transportation, construction, and industries. Vehicle emissions are the most significant contributors to poor air quality along main roads, whereas domestic stoves are the most significant contributor in rural areas Rwanda environmental management authority [29] Air pollution in urban and rural areas is made up of a complex mix of chemicals, particulate matter, and biological materials, all of which can lead to respiratory issues, chronic diseases, and early death[31]. more than 2,000 deaths per year were related to ambient air pollution as of earlier years and which is a major risk factor for respiratory disorders in Rwanda [29] .Rwanda opted to create solutions for these tragic problems by creating the first ecofriendly park in Kigali, In 2016, the Government of Rwanda through the Rwanda Environment Management Authority (REMA) developed the Nyandungu restoration project to respond to these challenges and demonstrate the potential of wetlands to abate pollution and reduce the risk of flooding in urban areas, The Nyandungu eco park, formerly a deteriorated swamp, is now an educational and recreational eco-park in Rwanda's capital city. Nyandungu is a recreational park that is open to the public. The restoration of the Nyandungu wetland and the establishment of an eco-tourism park resulted in the planting of 17,000 trees of 55 indigenous species. A medical garden, a Pope's Garden, five catchment ponds, three pleasure ponds, an information center, a restaurant, and 10 kilometers of pathways and bike lanes are all part of the 121-hectare park. . Kigali's rapid expansion and associated human activities have put significant strain on the wetlands. Wetlands, especially Nyandungu, have been damaged, resulting in a loss of

biodiversity. Encroachment has also caused downstream flooding and increased pollution owing to sewage overflows. The conversion of Nyandungu Wetland into an eco-tourism park exemplifies Rwanda's efforts and commitment to environmental protection, notably for the conservation of wetland habitats and eco-tourism. "Investing in nature is the best investment we can make." The deputy CEO of RDB said [32], By protecting and restoring our ecosystems, we create jobs, improve people's well-being, and strengthen community resilience to climate change and extreme weather events [31]. According to the discussion from the authorities the government plans to build five more eco public parks in the Kigali cities' wetlands. This will be a huge add to the city's greenery and to reducing climate change effects.

Fig. 2: Nyandungu Eco-Park

Conclusion

In the human history, green environment has always provided the most refuge and shelter. In the antiquity human being found shelter in the forest and hats in the trees living with animals as he is himself. In the coming of civilization man has developed to the extent that was never predicted in the history of the universe. The creation of concrete, tarmac roads, highways, hundred-meter-tall building, the pyramid in Egypt and elsewhere. All these shows how far the human has come. Nevertheless, the thirst to build more is there however facing several challenges and creating catastrophes for himself the human being needs to come back to the root. in the recent decades African cities. As good as the development is welcomed it is no longer the pre-colonial times. the development is very needed but it needs to be sustainable otherwise cities would be attempting to kill more birds only to see that the slingshot lacks a stone. Public parks do not only serve the city but on individual level citizens need to breathe and breathing is a right to every human being whether in rural or urban areas. provide a viable means to improve air quality through pollution removal and other tree functions (e.g., air temperature reductions), urban trees can help improve air quality for many different air pollutants in cities, and consequently can help improve human health. While the existing percent air quality improvements due to pollution removal by urban trees are modest, they can be improved by increasing urban tree canopy cover. The combined total effects of trees on air pollutants are significant enough that urban tree

management could provide a viable means to improve air quality[33]. The green city, with its lush vegetation, emerges as a common ideal that transcends time, material and cultural differences. Green infrastructure refers to urban vegetation that comes in many forms and serves many purposes. Street trees, green lanes, green roofs, green walls, urban parks, and informal green spaces are all examples of places where vegetation is present. They can be constructed from scratch, adapted from pre-urbanization natural bequest, spontaneously colonized on ruderal sites, or inherited as remaining natural enclaves. The urban heat island effect, for example, will increase the intensity and frequency of heat waves, disabling critical infrastructure and increasing death and morbidity[34]. Longer and more frequent instances of urban climate moving beyond human comfort zones will plague residents, increasing energy use and the associated pollution implications. Climate change, when combined with increasingly unpredictable precipitation and gradual sea-level rises, is predicted to have a profound influence on metropolitan populations[35]. With more than half of humankind residing in cities, many of which are plagued by chronic climatic and ecological stressors, urban people are likely to bear the brunt of the effects of climate change. Green infrastructure is a local response to the world's most serious challenge today. The many sustainable ecosystem services that urban greenery provides in a cost-effective and efficient manner have the potential to safeguard cities from the detrimental effects of climate change. By harnessing and combining natural processes with conventional infrastructure development, green infrastructure can help mitigate natural hazards, control water balance, and alleviate heat stress. It has the potential to improve cities' and citizens' climate resilience.

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Guillaume Niyontezeho.

